

Satisfaction Towards Scooter Purchase Among Women Purchaser

Dr. K. NATARAJAN

**Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar – 608002, Tamilnadu, India. Mail [id-natarajank.mbaau@gmail.com](mailto:dr-natarajank.mbaau@gmail.com)
(On Deputation to Thiru Kolanjiappar Govt. Arts College, Vriddhachalam)**

Abstract

Customer satisfaction is a feeling or pleasure. Consumer satisfaction is a central concept in modern marketing thought and practice. The marketing concept emphasizes delivering satisfaction to consumers and obtaining profits in return. As a result, overall quality of life is expected to be enhanced. Thus, consumer satisfaction is crucial to meeting various needs of consumers, business, and society. Satisfaction is similar to attitude in that it can be assessed as the sum of the satisfaction with the various attributes of the product or service. Indians prefer the scooters because of their small manageable size, low maintenance, pricing and easy loan repayment. Motorized scooters are seen as a symbol of status by the people. The objective of scooter industry is to sustain market share through satisfying customer needs and expectations. With an expanding market and entry of new players over the last few years, the Indian scooter industry is now approaching a stage of maturity. Previously, there were only a handful of scooter models available in the country. Currently, India is the second largest producer of scooters in the world. It stands next only to China and Japan in terms of the number of scooters produced and the sales respectively. Today most of the customer preferred to buy scooter instead of motorcycles. In recent days government also imposed emission norms which convert the purchasing behavior of the consumer. This article describes how women scooter buyer prefer to buy among different brand of scooters in the market and their satisfaction level with the features of the different brands of scooters.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, scooters, Consumer preference, women purchaser, brands

I – INTRODUCTION

Satisfaction is a major outcome of marketing activity and serves to link processes culminating in purchase and consumption with post purchase phenomena such as attitude change, repeat purchase, and brand loyalty. The centrality of the concept is reflected by its inclusion in the marketing concept that profits are generated through the satisfaction of consumer needs and wants. Consumer satisfaction also differs in their level of specificity. Commonly employed levels include consumer satisfaction with a product, with a consumption experience, with a purchase decision experience, with the salesperson, with a store, with an attribute and with a pre-purchase experience. Two wheeler industries slowdown has lasted for over a year and impacted sales of commuter motor cycles, Two-wheelers have seen their sales plunge by 88 percent in March and by 27 percent in Financial Year 2020. Hero Motocorp, which has 37.74 percent of the two-wheeler market share, and Hero has a strong hold, the Financial Year 2020 numbers are understandably low: 11 percent down

YoY at 64,09,719 units (FY2019: 72,39,460). Honda Motorcycle & Scooter India, the No. 2 industry player in two-wheelers with 27 percent market share, recorded domestic market sales of 245,699 units in March 2020, Motorcycle and scooter manufacturer the TVS Motor Co, which is the No. 3 in the industry by virtue of its 14 percent market share, has also been mauled by the slowdown. Suzuki Motorcycle India, possibly the only OEM has registered a 5.7 percent growth in Financial Year 2020 over Financial Year 2019 with 790,397 units compared to 747,506 units in Financial Year 2019. Important players in the sector markets are India Yamaha Motor Private Limited and Eicher Motors Limited, recent directives from the Niti Aayog, induce the producer to launch electric bikes. The Indian government's unforeseen announcements regarding the norms of BS-VI transition and the electrification of two-wheelers by 2025 have made the market volatile. However, the automobile sector is expected to recover by mid-Financial Year 2021 as per market speculations.

Top 10 Scooters Sale in India

	Models	February 2020
1	Honda Activa	2,22,961
2	Suzuki Access	50,103
3	TVS Jupiter	31,440
4	Honda Dio	26,494
5	Yamaha Fascino	25,709
6	TVS Ntorq	22,804
7	Yamaha Ray	11,348
8	Hero Pleasure	8,435
9	Suzuki Burgman Street	7,626
10	Hero Destini 125	7,304

Source: <https://www.autocarpro.in>

II – REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Brand image is defined as the consumer perception of a brand and is measured as the brand associations held in the consumer memory. Duggani Yuvaraju (2014) study found that there is a difference of opinion between in the factors like mileage, pickup, price and design. Injazz J.Chen (2003) has found in their study that Customer relationship management is a combination of people, processes and technology that seeks to understand a company's customers and companies that successfully implement CRM will reap the rewards in customer loyalty and long run profitability. Anuj kumar Kanojia, (2011) in his study explored the impact of consumer preference on sale of scooters in urban areas of India and found that urban and rural regions have different preferences when it comes to selecting the vehicle model. Alok Saklani et. al. (2000) analyzed the scooter buyers with the objective to locate the threshold to high satisfaction. Information on prior expectations has collected from the scooter buyers. It is found to supports the common belief that higher satisfaction is more likely when performance exceeds expectation rather than when it merely equals the same. Saraswathi, S. (2008) study shows that the key to success lies not only in having a good product, but also in being able to provide the customer with the level of service they desire.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the demographic attributes and satisfaction level of women customer
- To identify the satisfaction level of women customer towards purchase of scooter
- To know the future purchase opinion among women purchaser
- To identify the factors which influence women customer purchase decision

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is focused to know the customer satisfaction level towards women scooter buyer and also can identify which is the popular brand among the women buyer. The study was conducted during January 2020 and February 2020 and the data were collected from the women scooter users from different category of women such as Government employee, business women, private employees, students, retired person, agricultural related workers and self help group members from Cuddalore district of Tamilnadu and the number of sample limited to 100 due to time and money constraints.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was limited to women scooter buyer. The sample size of the study is limited 100 women scooter buyer. The women who possessed scooters were selected for the study and the study results cannot be generalized as the number of sample is small. The study results may not be applicable in other part of the country. The study was carried out during January 2020 and February 2020.

III – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

COLLECTION OF PRIMARY DATA

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a structured questionnaire administered in person from the respondents regarding their opinion about their satisfaction level of scooters among women. The respondents of this study were women scooter buyer. The researcher personally met the respondents, and data collection has been done only after establishing personal rapport with the respondents. The researcher has totally collected 100 responses for the present study. Hence, the sample of 100 is considered for this study and a total of 100 responses were obtained during January 2020 and February 2020.

COLLECTION OF SECONDARY DATA

The researcher collected secondary data on scooter sales, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the purchase action. This information has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

First hand information is collected from 100 respondents. Responses were coded and data entered and then analysed using a computer programme called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis were used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories, percentage analysis, one –way ANOVA and ranking method were used for this study.

IV – RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Age	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Age	18-25 Years	17	17.0	17.0
	25-30 Years	20	20.0	37.0
	30-35 Years	28	28.0	65.0
	35-40 Years	11	11.0	76.0
	40-45 Years	15	15.0	91.0
	45 and Above	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Educational Qualification	Below 8 th	10	10.0	10.0
	10 th Std	15	15.0	25.0
	HSC	7	7.0	32.0
	UG	23	23.0	55.0
	PG	27	27.0	82.0
	M.Phil	9	9.0	91.0
	Others	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Income Level	Less than 5000	27	27.0	27.0
	Rs 5000-10000	22	22.0	49.0
	Rs. 10000-15000	24	24.0	73.0
	Rs 15000-20000	12	12.0	85.0
	Rs. 20000 – 25000	3	3.0	88.0
	Rs. 25000 – 30000	3	3.0	91.0
	Rs. 30000 and above	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Nature of Job	Govt. Employee	12	12.0	12.0
	Business women	6	6.0	18.0
	Private Employees	29	29.0	47.0
	Student	15	15.0	62.0
	Retired Person	2	2.0	64.0
	Farmer	30	30.0	94.0
	Self Help Group	6	6.0	100.0

	Total	100	100.0	23.0
Brand of Scooter	Honda	23	23.0	23.0
	TVS	37	37.0	60.0
	Yamaha	18	18.0	78.0
	Bajaj	2	2.0	80.0
	Hero	16	16.0	96.0
	Suzuki	4	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Year of Owning Vehicle	1 Year	10	10.0	10.0
	2 Years	28	28.0	38.0
	3 Years	38	38.0	76.0
	Years	10	10.0	86.0
	5 Years	10	10.0	96.0
	Above 5 Years	4	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 1 shows the profile of the respondents, among the respondents 20 percent of the respondents belongs to the age group of 25-30 and 28 percent of the respondents belongs to the age group of 30-35 years. Regarding the educational qualification of respondents 27 percent of them are post graduates and 23 percent of them are under graduates and 15 percent of the respondents are having the qualification of 10th standard. In case of income level, 27 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 5000 per month and below, 22 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 5000-10,000 per month, 24 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 1000-15000 per month. Regarding the occupation 30 percent of the respondents are doing farming related works, 29 percent of the respondents are private employees, 15 percent of them are students and 6 percent of the respondents are belongs to self help group. Among the respondents 37 percent of them having TVS vehicle, 23 percent of the respondents having Honda brand of scooters and 18 percent of them having Yamaha. Regarding the years of ownership of the vehicle, 38 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for last 3 years, 28 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for 2 years.

Table 2: ANOVA Table: Relationship between the Demographic Attributes of the Respondents and Satisfaction Level

Demographic Variables		N	Mean	SD	F	Sig.
Age	18-25 Years	17	4.00	.866	9.777	.000
	25-30 Years	20	3.80	.834		
	30-35 Years	28	3.75	.967		
	35-40 Years	11	3.00	1.000		
	40-45 Years	15	2.33	.617		
	45 and Above	9	2.78	.441		

Qualification	Below 8 th	10	3.10	.738	2.795	.015*
	10 th Std	15	3.20	1.146		
	HSC	7	3.86	1.069		
	UG	23	3.91	.793		
	PG	27	2.96	1.055		
	M.Phil	9	3.78	.833		
	Others	9	3.56	1.014		
Monthly Income	Less than 5000	27	3.74	.944	3.844	.002*
	Rs 5000-10000	22	3.41	.908		
	Rs. 10000-15000	24	2.88	1.035		
	Rs 15000-20000	12	4.00	1.044		
	Rs. 20000 – 25000	3	4.33	.577		
	Rs. 25000 – 30000	3	3.67	1.155		
	Rs. 30000 and above	9	2.78	.441		
Occupation	Govt. Employee	12	3.58	1.165	2.432	.031*
	Business women	6	3.67	.816		
	Private Employees	29	3.28	.960		
	Student	15	4.20	.862		
	Retired Person	2	3.00	.000		
	Farmer	30	3.10	1.029		
	Self Help Group	6	3.33	.816		
	Total	100	3.42	1.017		

Source: primary Data (* significant at 5 percent level)

Table – 2 shows the Relationship between the Demographic Attributes of the Respondents and their Satisfaction Level, the data were grouped on the basis of age of the respondents, educational qualification, monthly income and occupation. Mean value and standard deviation value were calculated for each group. From the ANOVA test it is found that there is significant difference in the mean scores of the Demographic Attributes of the Respondents on Age, educational qualification, monthly income and Occupation.

Table – 3 Respondent’s satisfaction level with product features and Age

Factors	Age, Mean Value and (SD)						F-Value	P-Value
	18-25 Years (17)	25-30 Years (20)	30-35 Years (28)	35-40 Years (11)	40-45 Years (15)	45 and Above (9)		
Design	4.29 (0.686)	4.65 (0.813)	4.5 (0.694)	4.73 (0.467)	4.07 (1.163)	4.44 (0.527)	1.444	.216
Price	4.18 (0.951)	3.45 (1.572)	4.71 (0.535)	3.82 (1.079)	4 (0.756)	4.33 (0.707)	4.162	.002*
Power	3.59 (0.939)	3.35 (0.875)	4.21 (0.787)	4.27 (0.905)	3.93 (0.884)	4.11 (0.782)	3.361	.008*
Maintenance	2.71 (0.985)	3.3 (0.979)	3.54 (0.838)	4.36 (0.674)	3.93 (0.799)	3 (1)	6.229	.000

Mileage	3.88 (1.054)	3.6 (1.142)	4.21 (0.787)	4.09 (0.701)	4.07 (0.704)	4.22 (0.833)	1.305	.268
Resale-value	3.29 (0.772)	3.5 (0.946)	2.57 (0.836)	3.82 (0.751)	3.87 (0.64)	3.33 (0.5)	7.488	.000
Status	3.53 (0.8)	3.3 (1.129)	3.52 (1.087)	4.45 (0.82)	4.07 (0.884)	3.67 (0.707)	2.746	.023*
Reputation	3.71 (1.359)	3.2 (1.105)	4.29 (0.713)	4.73 (0.467)	3.8 (0.862)	4 (0.866)	4.938	.000
Spare Availability	3.41 (1.064)	3.5 (1.235)	3.75 (0.701)	4.36 (1.027)	4.07 (0.884)	4.11 (0.928)	2.088	.074
After sale service	3.41 (1.004)	3.25 (1.293)	2.89 (1.286)	4.18 (0.603)	3.93 (0.704)	3.67 (0.707)	3.378	.008*
E-Starter	3.88 (0.6)	4.25 (1.164)	4.04 (1.374)	4.09 (0.831)	4.07 (0.961)	3.78 (0.667)	.349	.882
Safety	3.47 (1.125)	4.25 (0.786)	3.5 (1.139)	4.09 (0.944)	4.2 (0.676)	4.33 (0.866)	2.874	.019*
Break	3.59 (1.121)	3.9 (0.912)	3.82 (1.124)	4.82 (0.405)	4.13 (0.834)	4.33 (0.707)	2.775	.022*
Storage	3.76 (1.147)	3.75 (1.07)	3.86 (0.848)	4.18 (0.982)	3.93 (0.961)	4 (1)	.355	.878
Attribute-Wheel Size	3.82 (1.02)	4.6 (0.82)	3.5 (1.32)	4.36 (0.67)	4.2 (0.78)	4.67 (0.71)	4.063	.002*
Seat	4.24 (0.664)	4.35 (0.875)	3.96 (0.576)	4.45 (0.688)	4.27 (0.594)	4.67 (0.500)	2.010	.084
Length Weight	4 (1.000)	3.9 (0.641)	4.56 (0.698)	4.64 (0.505)	4.13 (0.834)	4.33 (0.707)	2.800	.021*
Design Lamp	3.65 (1.057)	3.75 (0.967)	3.54 (1.138)	4.45 (0.934)	4.2 (0.775)	4.22 (0.667)	2.216	.059
Comfort Ride	3.65 (0.862)	3.9 (1.165)	4.36 (0.780)	4.27 (0.647)	3.67 (0.900)	4.22 (0.441)	2.318	.049*

Source: primary Data (* significant at 5 percent level)

Table – 3 shows the satisfaction level of respondents with product features and age of the respondents. To know the satisfaction level of the different age group of the respondents with product feature, the researcher considered various product features such as Design of scooter, price, power, maintenance, mileage, resale value, status, reputation, spares availability, after sale service, e-starter, safety, break, storage capacity, wheel size, seating comfort, length and weight, design lamp and comfort ride. To know the satisfaction level of the respondents with product features and age of the respondents ANOVA test was carried out.

H1: There is no significance difference of opinion on satisfaction among the different age group of respondents with product features

To test the hypothesis, ANOVA test was carried out, the results shows that the different age group of the respondents satisfaction level varies with some product features, because the f value is greater than p value such features are price of the scooter, power, maintenance, resale value, status, reputation, after sale service, safety, break, wheel size, length and weight, and comfort ride. But in some product features such as Design of scooter, mileage, spares availability, e-starter, storage capacity, seating comfort, design lamp there is no significance difference of opinion among the various age groups of the respondents with product features.

Table – 4 Respondent’s satisfaction level with Brand and Product Features

Factors	Age, Mean Value and (SD)						F-Value	P-Value
	Honda 23	TVS 37	Yamaha 18	Bajaj 2	Hero 16	Suzuki 4		
Design	4.61 (0.783)	4.24 (0.895)	4.33 (0.767)	5 (0)	4.69 (0.479)	4.75 (0.5)	1.423	.223
Price	3.96 (1.296)	4.24 (0.83)	4 (1.237)	4.5 (0.707)	4.13 (1.147)	4.5 (1)	.388	.856
Power	3.52 (0.898)	4.05 (0.78)	3.67 (1.188)	5 (0)	4.06 (0.68)	4.25 (0.957)	2.172	.064
Maintenance	3.09 (0.996)	3.76 (0.895)	3.17 (1.15)	4 (0)	3.56 (0.964)	3.25 (0.957)	1.868	.107
Mileage	3.74 (1.054)	4.14 (0.751)	3.44 (1.042)	5 (0)	4.5 (0.516)	4.25 (0.5)	3.886	.003*
Resale-value	3.17 (0.937)	3.49 (0.87)	2.94 (0.998)	3.5 (0.707)	3.38 (0.885)	3 (0.816)	1.068	.383
Status	3.3 (1.02)	4 (0.913)	3.29 (1.105)	3 (0)	3.88 (0.957)	4 (0.816)	2.428	.041*
Reputation	3.83 (0.937)	4.14 (0.887)	3.5 (1.295)	4.5 (0.707)	4.06 (1.237)	3.5 (0.577)	1.270	.283
Spare Availability	3.83 (0.937)	4.11 (0.843)	3 (0.97)	4.5 (0.707)	3.88 (1.147)	3.5 (0.577)	3.770	.004*
After sale service	3.35 (1.265)	3.68 (0.944)	2.89 (1.323)	3.5 (0.707)	3.56 (1.153)	3.25 (0.5)	1.282	.278
E-Starter	4.22 (0.951)	4.05 (0.911)	3.67 (1.572)	4 (1.414)	4.13 (0.719)	4.25 (0.957)	.637	.672
Safety	3.96 (0.976)	4 (0.882)	3.17 (1.249)	5 (0)	4.06 (0.772)	4.5 (1)	3.097	.012*
Break	3.87 (1.1)	4.11 (0.994)	3.56 (0.984)	4.5 (0.707)	4.31 (0.793)	4.25 (0.957)	1.378	.240
Storage	3.7 (1.146)	3.78 (0.947)	3.72 (0.895)	4.5 (0.707)	4.31 (0.793)	4.5 (1)	1.473	.206
Attribute-Wheel Size	4.09 (1.083)	3.92 (1.115)	4.11 (0.963)	4.5 (0.707)	4.31 (1.078)	4.25 (1.500)	.391	.854
Seat	4.26 (0.810)	4.16 (0.727)	4.17 (0.514)	4.5 (0.707)	4.5 (0.632)	4.25 (0.500)	.640	.670
Length Weight	4 (0.853)	4.35 (0.716)	4.28 (0.752)	4.5 (0.707)	4.33 (0.900)	4.25 (0.957)	.654	.660
Design Lamp	3.83 (0.937)	3.95 (1.026)	3.44 (1.199)	5 (0.000)	3.94 (0.929)	4.25 (0.500)	1.324	.261
Comfort Ride	4.22 (0.671)	4.11 (0.699)	3.5 (1.383)	4 (0.000)	4.06 (0.680)	4.25 (1.500)	1.606	.166

Source: primary Data (* significant at 5 percent level)

Table – 4 shows the satisfaction level of respondents with Brand and product features of the product. To know the satisfaction level of the respondents with product features and Brand, the researcher considered various Brands such as Honda, TVS, Yamaha, Bajaj, Hero, Suzuki and product features such as Design, price, power, maintenance, mileage, resale value, status, reputation, spares availability, after sale service, e-starter, safety, break, storage capacity, wheel size, seating comfort, length and weight, design lamp and comfort ride. To know the satisfaction level of the respondents with product features and brand ANOVA test was carried out.

H2: There is no significance difference of opinion on satisfaction with Brand and product features

To test the hypothesis, ANOVA test was carried out; the results shows that the respondent's satisfaction level varies with some product features with brand, because the f value is greater than p value such features are mileage, status, and spares availability. There is no significant difference of opinion in some product features and brands are Design of scooter, price, power, maintenance, resale value, reputation, after sale service, e-starter, break, storage capacity, wheel size, seating comfort, length and weight, design lamp and comfort ride.

Table – 5 Respondents Opinion on Future Purchase of scooter

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	63	63.0	63.0
No	21	21.0	84.0
Cannot Say	16	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 5 shows the respondents opinion on repeat purchase of the same scooter brand. The respondents expressed their willingness to buy same brand of scooters in future too. Among the respondents 63 percent of the respondents will repeat to buy same brands of scooters, 21 percent of the respondents says that they will not repeat to buy same brand of scooter and 16 percent of them expressed that they cannot say the repeat purchase of the same brand.

Table – 6 Respondents Opinion on after sale service

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	86	86.0	86.0
No	14	14.0	100.0
Total	100	100	

Source: primary Data

Table – 6 shows the respondents opinion on the after sale service of the scooter company, the result shows that 86 percent of respondents are happy about the performance on after sale service and 14 percent of the respondents are unhappy with performance of the sale service of the company.

Table – 7 Overall Satisfaction of the Respondent

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Highly Satisfied	41	41.0	41.0
Satisfied	27	27.0	68.0
Neutral	22	22.0	90.0
Dissatisfied	7	7.0	97.0
Highly Dissatisfied	3	3.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 7 shows the overall satisfaction level of the respondents, among the respondents 41 percent of them are highly satisfied with the performance of the scooter, 27 percent of the respondents says that they are satisfied on the performance of the scooter, 22 percent of the respondents says that they cannot say anything regarding the performance of the scooter and only 3 percent of the respondents say that they are highly dissatisfied.

V – FINDINGS

From the study it is found that among the respondents 20 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 25-30 and 28 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 30-35 years. In educational qualification of respondents 27 percent of them are post graduates and 23 percent of them are under graduates and 15 percent of the respondents are having the qualification of 10th standard. Regarding the occupation 30 percent of the respondents are doing farming related works, 29 percent of the respondents are private employees, 15 percent of them are students and 6 percent of the respondents are belongs to self help group. Among the respondents 37 percent of them having TVS scooters, 23 percent of the respondents having Honda brand of scooters 18 percent of them having Yamaha brands. Regarding the years of ownership of the vehicle, 38 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for last 3 years, 28 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for 2 years.

ANOVA result found that there is significant difference in the mean scores of the Demographic Attributes of the Respondents on Age, educational qualification, monthly income and Occupation.

It is found that satisfaction level varies with some product features and the different age group of the respondent, such features is price of the scooters, power, maintenance, resale value, status, reputation, after sale service, safety, break, wheel size, length and weight, and comfort ride. But in some product features such as Design of scooters, mileage, spares availability, e-starter, storage capacity, seating comfort, design lamp there is no difference of opinion among the various age groups of the respondents with product features.

The results shows that the respondent satisfaction level varies with some product features with brand, such features are mileage, status, and spares availability. There is no difference of opinion in some product features and brands are Design of scooter, price, power, maintenance, resale value, reputation, after sale service, e-starter, break, storage capacity, wheel size, seating comfort, length and weight, design lamp and comfort ride.

It is found that among the respondent 63 percent of them will buy same brands of scooters, 21 percent of the respondents says that they will not repeat to buy same brand of scooter and 16 percent of them expressed that they cannot say the repeat purchase of the same brand. So it can be concluded that most of the respondent are happy with the same brand.

The result shows that 86 percent of respondents are happy about the performance on after sale service and 14 percent of the respondents are unhappy with performance of the sale service of the company. So it is concluded that the company's performance also satisfying the buyer through after sale service.

VI – CONCLUSION

Customer satisfaction is very important in any product, when customer is happy with a specific brand or features they will be happy to repeat to buy the same brand. Today Marketing plays an important role and there is a need to fulfill the needs and wants of the customer's satisfaction. The level of satisfaction towards quality of product and other related features in a specific brand of a scooter is very important. Hence, the company must concentrate on measuring and understanding the factors which affect customer satisfaction.

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